

DTwA Digital Entity Aggregation

- DTwA user
- Domain expert

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- Domain expert

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- Domain expert

DTws Models
Aggregation

DTws Data
Resources
Aggregation

DTws Services
Referenciation

DTwA Model / DTws
Model References +
Instantiation

DTwA Data
Resources / DTws
Data Resources
References +
Instantiation

DTws Services
References +
Instantiation